

IAM4NFDI

IAM4NFDI - Report on Security Operations

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1. Summary	2
2. Introduction.....	2
3. Security Risk Analysis.....	2
3.1 Assumptions	2
3.2. Vulnerabilities and Their Severity.....	2
3.3. Security Assessment Methodology	3
3.3.1. Automated Vulnerability Scans	3
3.3.2. Manual Checks.....	3
3.3.3. Infrastructure Tests.....	3
4. Documentation and Architecture Review	4
4.1. Risk Assessment of Individual Components	4
4.1.1. NFDI Infrastructure Proxy.....	4
4.1.2. AcademicID.....	4
4.1.3. didmos.....	4
4.1.4. RegApp	4
4.1.5. Unity	5
4.2. Results of the Vulnerability Scans.....	5
5. Conclusion and Outlook	5

1. Summary

IAM4NFDI (Identity and Access Management for the National Research Data Infrastructure) is a central core service for managing identities and access rights within the NFDI. This security report documents the current security status of IAM4NFDI and describes identified vulnerabilities that could affect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and services.

2. Introduction

This security report was prepared to provide a comprehensive overview of the security status of IAM4NFDI. The scope of this report covers all components of IAM4NFDI, i.e., the NFDI Infrastructure Proxy as well as the four community AAls: AcademicID, didmos, Unity, and RegApp. The security assessment is based on technical measures such as vulnerability analyses, code reviews, and configuration checks.

The architecture and basic functionality of IAM4NFDI are described in detail in the documents within the IAM4NFDI Operating Concept (IAM4NFDI Service Description, Operating Concept, and TOMs)¹ and in the IAM4NFDI Service Onboarding Handbook² and will not be repeated here. This report focuses explicitly on technical security aspects and not on organizational or procedural measures.

3. Security Risk Analysis

3.1 Assumptions

The following security assessment is based on the following assumptions:

- IAM4NFDI is operated in a secure cloud environment.
- The underlying infrastructure (e.g., servers, network) is adequately secured.
- Users of IAM4NFDI comply with
 - 1) the security policies of their respective home institutions,
 - 2) the security and terms of use of the service provider, and
 - 3) the technical and organizational framework established by the CAAI operators.

3.2. Vulnerabilities and Their Severity

Security vulnerabilities are technical or organizational flaws in software, system configurations, or services that provide attackers with an unintended opportunity to compromise systems or extract sensitive data. The CVE system (³) is used internationally for the standardized tracking of such vulnerabilities. Each vulnerability is assigned a unique CVE ID and rated according to its criticality using the CVSS (Common Vulnerability Scoring System) score.

The CVSS rating is on a scale from 0.0 to 10.0 and is typically categorized into severity levels:

- Low (0.1 – 3.9): low impact, rarely exploitable
- Medium (4.0 – 6.9): potentially exploitable, significant security implications
- High (7.0 – 8.9): significant risk, urgent action required
- Critical (9.0 – 10.0): Immediate, serious risk, immediate action required

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/13149756>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/15629651>

³ <https://www.cve.org/>

3.3. Security Assessment Methodology

Various methods and measures are used to assess the security of an IT system. These serve to systematically document security-related aspects, identify risks, and regularly review the effectiveness of existing protective mechanisms.

3.3.1. Automated Vulnerability Scans

Automated vulnerability scans are used to efficiently and systematically check systems for known security vulnerabilities. In this process, the analyzed components are compared against current CVE databases. Tools such as OpenVAS / Greenbone Vulnerability Management⁴ and Nessus⁵ were used in the project. These solutions automatically identify potential vulnerabilities, map them to the corresponding CVE entries, and assess their severity using CVSS scores.

Automated scans provide a fast, comprehensive analysis and are particularly suitable for regular repetition to continuously monitor the security status of systems. *They should be directly integrated into the development process, meaning they should be performed automatically within the context of CI/CD platforms, at the latest during release builds. Ideally, this is done via automatically generated SBOMs (Software Bill of Materials), “a machine-readable file containing details and supply chain relationships of the components used in a software application”⁶.* An SBOM can then be compared with a vulnerability database, such as the CVE databases⁷, to determine whether the software’s artifacts are affected by vulnerabilities.

3.3.2. Manual Checks

Manual checks complement automated scans by assessing individual configurations, logical errors, and context-dependent risks. These include, for example:

- Evaluation of security-related settings
- Analysis of role and permission models
- Review of security parameters that automated tools cannot reliably detect
- Manual analyses provide a more precise assessment and help evaluate false positives or verify critical vulnerabilities more accurately.

3.3.3. Infrastructure Tests

Infrastructure tests examine the underlying technical systems on which the components are operated. These include, among others:

- Network and firewall configurations
- Operating system hardening
- Patch and update status

These tests identify system-wide and platform-related risks that are not necessarily linked to a single application but significantly impact its security.

⁴ <https://www.openvas.org>

⁵ <https://www.tenable.com/products/nessus>

⁶ See BSI: Technical Guideline TR-03183: Cyber Resilience Requirements for Manufacturers and Products – Part 2: Software Bill of Materials (SBOM)

<https://www.bsi.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/BSI/Publikationen/TechnischeRichtlinien/TR03183/BSI-TR-03183-2.pdf>

⁷ See <https://www.cve.org/>

4. Documentation and Architecture Review

In addition to technical tests, an evaluation of the existing documentation and architecture is also advisable. This includes:

- Analysis of system architecture and data flows
- Review of security concepts, role models, and interfaces
- Comparison of documentation with best practices (e.g., least privilege, zero trust)

This approach helps identify conceptual weaknesses, missing security mechanisms, or unclear responsibilities that could lead to risks during day-to-day operations.

4.1. Risk Assessment of Individual Components

A vulnerability scan was performed for each IAM4NFDI component. The results of these analyses are examined in more detail below with regard to the identified vulnerabilities, their potential exploitability, the possible damage, and the resulting risk assessment.

In addition, each operator has its own security operations processes, which were applied as a supplement and incorporated into the assessment of the respective component.

4.1.1. NFDI Infrastructure Proxy

For this report, an external vulnerability scan was performed on August 6, 2025, using OpenVAS (Greenbone Vulnerability Management). The scan was conducted via the public internet to assess the component from the perspective of an external attacker. An operating system scan was not part of the analysis. Additionally, a port scan was performed to identify accessible services and potential attack surfaces.

4.1.2. AcademicID

An external vulnerability scan was performed for the AcademicID on October 2, 2025. The scan was conducted using Nessus and covered all relevant services, including web servers, APIs, and the underlying host systems. A port scan was also performed to identify open and accessible services.

One significant finding concerned a Redis service; however, this was operated exclusively in the development environment and has since been shut down. An operating system scan was not part of the analysis.

4.1.3. didmos

For this report, a vulnerability scan was performed on September 23, 2025, using Greenbone, deployed in a Docker container according to the official instructions. A basic scan was performed to check for known CVEs in all relevant components, including OpenLDAP, MongoDB, hostnames, web servers, and APIs. Additionally, a port scan was conducted to identify open and accessible ports, as well as all relevant hostnames and services in the didmos environment.

An SBOM is generated automatically for didmos on a regular basis and cross-referenced with CVEs. Security vulnerabilities discovered in this manner are promptly addressed, taking criticality into account, provided that a corresponding update for the affected component is available.

4.1.4. RegApp

For this component, the platform under consideration comprises several core technologies: the Debian Linux operating system, the OpenJDK runtime environment, the PostgreSQL database, the

OpenLDAP directory service, and various web servers. All systems are kept up to date daily via regular operating system updates, ensuring that security-related fixes are applied promptly.

An OWASP scanner is integrated into the build pipeline for continuous monitoring. The scan is performed automatically with every build and must be successfully completed for a build to be released. In addition, KIT-CERT regularly performs port scans to identify open and accessible services.

The results of the respective checks are documented in the build reports. If vulnerabilities are identified in individual components, an update is performed to a version without the affected vulnerability—provided a corresponding update is available.

4.1.5. Unity

A basic scan was performed for this component, supplemented by a port scan to identify open and accessible services. The analysis was conducted using Nessus, with the scan executed via an agent installed on the system. The checks take place once a week and provide continuous security-related results.

If vulnerabilities are detected, the responsible system administrator is notified and asked to address the identified security gaps through appropriate measures—such as patches or configuration adjustments.

4.2. Results of the Vulnerability Scans

No serious vulnerabilities (with severity levels of “high” or “critical”) were identified in the scans performed. According to the operators, all vulnerabilities found were remedied via patches or software updates in accordance with standard security practices.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

IAM4NFDI represents a central component of NFDI’s security. The security assessment conducted shows that IAM4NFDI has a solid security foundation, but there is still room for improvement in certain areas.

Implementing the recommended measures will help further enhance security and ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and services on a long-term basis.

IAM4NFDI must comply with the requirements of the GDPR and the German IT Security Act ⁽⁸⁾. Regular compliance reviews are necessary to ensure that these requirements are met.

The following steps are planned:

- Development of a detailed action plan for implementing the identified security measures.
- Further automation of vulnerability scans
- Conducting a penetration test in the upcoming project phase (2026) to verify the effectiveness of the measures and identify any potential additional—including as-yet-undiscovered—vulnerabilities.

⁸ See https://www.bgbl.de/xaver/bgbl/start.xav?startbk=Bundesanzeiger_BGBl&jumpTo=bgbl121s1122.pdf